

SYNTHESIS, SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION, AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF 2-*{(E)-[2-(diphenylmethyl)hydrazinylidene]methyl}*-3-METHYLPHENOL AND ITS Ni²⁺ AND Cu²⁺ COMPLEXES

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Abstract

We report the synthesis, characterization, and structural evaluation of a new compound resulting from the condensation reaction of 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (salicylaldehyde) with diphenylmethyl hydrazine. The reaction was conducted under mild conditions which resulted in a high yield of the desired compound, 2-{(E)-[2-(diphenylmethyl)hydrazinylidene]methyl}*-3-methylphenol, (DHMP). We confirmed the structure of the synthesized Schiff base using several techniques, including FTIR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and UV-Vis spectroscopy. To check its purity, we performed elemental analysis, and for its thermal stability, we used thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Results showed significant structural stabilizing interactions such as hydrogen bonding and non-covalent interactions which may propose an insight into its coordination chemistry and possible biological activity. This produced compound has many values and can be utilized as drugs, catalysts and for many other industrial processes. This discovery contributes to the rising creation and application of hydrazone moieties.*

Keywords: Hydrazone, Spectroscopy, Synthesis, Characterization, Coordination.

INTRODUCTION

Hydrazones, are types of Schiff bases, they are substances in organic chemistry produced when hydrazines and carbonyl compounds reacts. They are identified by the availability of a carbon – nitrogen double bond, hydrazones are versatile in their application, which makes them useful in various fields, including catalysis, drug design antibiotics etc. [1]. Compounds having the triatomic grouping, $>C=N-N<$ are hydrazones. The presence of the $-N-N-$ bonds makes them different from other members of this class (Figure 1). Condensation and substitution increase the functionality of this group [2].

Figures 1 a and b: Synthetic and generalized Structures of typical hydrazones

Where: R¹ and R² = H, or any other substituent.

Generally, hydrazones undergo tautomerization between keto and enol forms (Figure 2). Another route for synthesizing hydrazone Schiff base ligands is by bond formation of diazonium compounds with compounds containing active H [3].

Figure 2: Tautomerism of hydrazones

Judging from the diagrammatic representation hydrazones have;

- i. electron donating nitrogen atom,
- ii. dual reactivity imine,
- iii. C=N bond-driven stereoisomerism
- iv. Often an acidic nitrogen atom [4].

The hydrazine group's chemical as well as physical properties are a result of these structural motifs, which also have a significant impact on the variety of applications that can be made use of by the group (Figure 3).

Figure 3: diagram showing functionalities of hydrazones

One of the salient features of these compounds is their high physiological activity [5]. An important family of compounds are hydrazones with an azomethine proton ($-\text{NHN}=\text{CH}-$), two of N atoms made of different backgrounds are seen to connect as well as a carbon – nitrogen double bond, delocalized with the lone electron pair on the terminal nitrogen atom (Figure 1.6). Numerous investigations have shown that the sp^2 -hybridized nitrogen atom which has a lone electron pair are responsible for the recorded activities of hydrazones [6]. Hydrazones are easily formed when compounds involving hydrazines or hydrazides are heated with carbonyl compounds with the suitable solvent. Aryldiazonium compounds and compounds containing active H can be condensed also to create hydrazones [7]. Hydrazones consists of substances with marked biological activities and are a widely applied group of ligands having undergone series of research over a period of time as possible versatile ligands with many modes of coordination [8].

A hydrazone's choice of coordination mode depends on a number of variables, including tautomerism, the circumstances of the reaction, ability of the formed complex to withstand heat and the tally and type attachments on its structure. Similarly, it is pertinent to infer that the usefulness of coordination complexes everyday life is on the increase because of their sustainable features. Possibilities of hydrazones to coordinate are improved the nature of the ligands which consist of N, and O atoms which are highly electronegative and improves the denticity. Hydrazone structures are attached with various donor points, Which often include O-N-O, N-N-O, N-O, and N-NS, and is the feature that equips the compounds with their high applicability. Hydrazones has a distinguished valuation among the ligand systems that are made up of nitrogen – oxygen arrangement; this is because of their simple synthetic route, flexibility, higher coordination modes and ability to form an array of compounds that have great importance chemically, structurally, biologically and industrially [9], [10], [11]. In this field, hydrazones are used as many-teethed ligands that can chelate chelate with metal atoms, especially those of transition origin.

Research have revealed that the applicability of the compounds are as a result of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group that contain a lone electron pair that has been hybridized on the nitrogen atom in an sp or sp^2 manner. Many scientists have created a number of fresh hydrazones and their metal complexes because of their numerous important properties. Metal ions of the d-block origin possess a special ability of complexation. Compounds formed by the transition metals with aromatic hydrazones and other Schiff bases [12], [13] have received great attention. The O, N, and S donor ligand hydrazone complexes' coordination potential and pharmacological significance have drawn particular attention to their chemistry and their applications in chemical analysis substances capable of extracting metals. In recent studies metal complexes are seen to possess more activity with less side effect than the parent

compound [14]. The C=N group in hydrazones possesses a high reactivity, because of the nucleophilic nature of the two nitrogen atoms and the ambivalent nature of the carbon atom.

One of the focal points of research on hydrazones is the possibility for them to undergo complexation with transition metal ions, as these metal complexes often demonstrate enhanced biological activities and catalytic properties [15], [16], [17]. The unique properties of hydrazones arise from their functional groups, which enable them to act as bidentate ligands. In particular, the hydrazone group (C=N-N) can coordinate to metal centers, forming chelates that improve stability and reactivity of the resulting metal complexes [3]. This chelation can significantly influence the electronic properties of the metals, often leading to improved biological efficacy, making hydrazones promising candidates for drug development and therapeutic applications. Literature has revealed the anticancer, antifungal, and antibacterial activities of metal complexes derived from hydrazones [18]. 2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (salicylaldehyde) is an aldehyde which is often studied due to its ability to form Schiff base derivatives that are stable. Hydrazones' adaptability makes them and their derivatives useful in numerous applications, which consist of chelation, anticancer, and anti-inflammation [5].

The prominence of hydrazones can be attributed to their modularity, simple synthesis, and stability against hydrolysis. However, the azomethine group's functional versatility, is actually what makes it useful in so many different contexts. Hydrazones are used in analytical chemistry for metal ion analysis in various samples because they produce colored complexes with metal ions. According to a study by [19], hydrazones serve as analytical reagents for spectrophotometrically determining Ni(II). In analytical chemistry, hydrazones are employed as agents for extracting metals. As chelating agents, hydrazides have also been utilized in analytical chemistry. According to [20], biscyclohexanone oxalyl dihydrazone is used to detect copper in a variety of materials, including paper pulp products, human serum, plants, and other materials. A pyridine-based hydrazone, has been utilized for the detection of copper in foods since they may easily undergo a variety of ring-closure processes [21]. In a slightly acidic, neutral, or slightly alkaline solution, a certain isonicotinic hydrazone formed a strongly colored substance with Hg^+ or Hg^{2+} [22]. Silver and mercury have been measured nephelometrically using the combination of Co^{3+} with a pyridine hydrazone. Metal ions with a variety of organic molecules react to produce solids or solutions that are often colorful and are employed as reagents for analysis. Further the use of hydrazones as reagent for analysis warrants that groups with certain pH ranges and the atoms for coordination are used in order for organic reagents to react with metal ions.

Low molecular weight compounds are found in streams of gas by estimating the formation of derivative of hydrazones that are aromatic. For instance, the core of an adsorption cartridge is DNP coated onto silica sorbent, HPLC with a UV detector can be used to examine the eluted hydrazone. Again, for the analysis of metal ions, hydrazones are reagents with excellent properties in organic chemistry. In the detection of Pd^{2+} , two compounds were used to achieve the desired result. The described method has been used for Pd^{2+} determination in materials [23]. Another derivative of hydrazone has been used to test Pd^{2+} . Diphenyl carbazone was used to perform spectrophotometric measurements on Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} derivatives [24]. This established methodology has been used to determine the Zn^{2+} content of pharmaceutical sample. A derivative of alizarin is utilized for the measurement of Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} [25]. A thiosemicarbazone derivative has been utilized for the analysis of Ni^{2+} in samples of alloy [26].

Coupling techniques that utilize hydrazone derivatives are utilized to combine drugs to certain antibodies against cancerous cells. In the acidic lysosomes of the cell, connection based on hydrazones are irreversibly broken where it serves its purpose, but unreactive at a pH around 7. As an antitubercular medication, many potent substances like iproniazide, which works similarly to isoniazide, are employed [27]. Nifuroxazide is used to treat constipation and avoid loss of water. It "neutralizes mycobacterial" in diarrhea. Its spectrum covers most enteropathogenic mycobacteria, including Shigella, E. coli, Salmonella, Staphylococci, Klebsiella, and Yersinia. The presence of a C=O

area and an OH group in these hydrazones may be the reason for their ability to combat methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* strains [28]. Commercialization of several hydrazide-hydrazone compounds Chagas disease is treated with nifurtimox, while intestinal infections are treated with nifuroxazide (D) [29]. These compounds can act as many-teethed ligands, based on the type of substitutions on the hydrazone skeleton. The synthesis antibacterial activity of hydrazone of [(2-Benzothiazolylthio) acetyl] hydraine against some microorganisms has been investigated [30], against the yeast-like fungi and bacteria that were tested, all of the chemicals are extremely effective. Hydrazones have antiviral action some agents, according to [31], 2-hydroxy-1-naphth-aldehydeiso-nicotinoylhydrazone has antimalarial properties, and [32] found that some derivatives had antitumor properties. The bactericidal properties of complexes of some hydrazone derivatives were investigated, the antibacterial efficacy of these complexes has been assessed by researchers, they observed that Cu^{2+} complexes are more active than Z^{2+} complexes with both hydrazones at each concentration. The following are listed the main biological functions of hydrazone derivatives. The antibacterial activities of an oxobutyrate derivative has been investigated through their synthesis. The investigated compound [29] demonstrated significant action against *S. aureus* and *Mycobacterium fortuitum*. Some derivatives of hydrazone were discovered to have antibacterial action at 3.9 g/mL by [33]. The hydrazone derivatives are employed as fungicides and to treat conditions like leprosy, leukemia, and mental illnesses Psychotic and psychoneurotic conditions are treated using a variety of substituted hydrazides. Strong antibacterial properties are exhibited by carboxylic acid hydrazides, that are boosted by coordination to the metal centres. A research on the potency of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) showed its value as a substance for biological applications. Additionally, 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine plays a significant role in toxicology as well as numerous biological and pharmaceutical products [34].

The synthesis of heterocyclic rings like indoles and pyrazoles using aryl hydrazones were carried out, a wide range of effects are produced by the biological action of these substances [35]. The therapy for many infections is combated by the emerging bacterial resistance. Owing to this observation, discovering of new substances is a continuous process. Today, numerous hydrazone derivatives are formed and their potency against bacteria evaluated. Mashayekhi and colleagues showed that hydrazone derivatives with an indole moiety showed potential antiplatelet activity [36].

The ortho-hydroxyl group provides extra sites for coordination as well as enhances its stability through intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Hydrazones produced from salicylaldehyde have been studied for their coordination ability with various transition metals, leading to a multitude of compounds with many characteristics and applications. Our target in the present research is to a new compound of hydrazone origin. The compound of concern is 2-[(E)-[2-(diphenylmethyl)hydrazinylidene]methyl]-3-methylphenol, which is formed by the reaction of 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde with diphenylmethyl hydrazine. We selected this compound for its exceptional structural features and untapped applications in coordination chemistry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Starting materials and instrumentation

$\text{MCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ and Ni^{2+}), diphenylmethyl hydrazine, and 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (salicylaldehyde) were gotten from Aldrich and applied without further purifying them. Standard protocols were followed in the purification of the solvents. The analytical laboratory Nsukka Nigeria carried out elemental analyses of C, H, and N. Using KBr pellets, FTIR spectra were captured using a Scitech 55C-20 FT-IR spectrophotometer. A Perkin Elmer Two Spectrophotometer (1100–200 nm) was used to run a UV-Vis spectra analysis on the compounds using a 10^{-3} M solution of Dimethylformamide. Using WTW conductivity cell and an Infitek CON-B600L conductivity meter,

molar conductance was measured on a solution of dimethylformamide containing approximately 1 mmol dm⁻³ at room temperature.

Synthesis of DHMP

DHMP has been prepared by condensing 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (salicylaldehyde) and diphenylmethyl hydrazine in the manner previously reported by [5], [6]. A solution containing 0.01 mole 2-hydroxy-6-methylbenzaldehyde in EtOH (20 mL) was mixed with solutions containing 0.01 mole diphenylmethyl hydrazine in EtOH (20 mL). 2 droplets piperidine were then added to the mixture as a condensing agent (Scheme 1). The obtained mixture was kept in a water bath to be reflux for three hours. Colored precipitate was obtained and sorted out overnight. From ethanol, these precipitates underwent filtering, washing, and recrystallization. After that, the samples were vacuum-dried over fused calcium chloride before being examined, producing 94% yield, m.p. (170–172 °C).

Scheme 1: Synthetic route for DHMP

Preparation of Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂

Direct reaction method was adopted in line with previously reported experiment [7], [8]. 0.01 mole of DHMP in 20 mL EtOH were treated with the respective solutions of the hydrated metal (II) chloride. The mixtures were refluxed, cooled and precipitates were separated out. The compounds underwent filtration, an ethanol and ether wash, and a vacuum-assisted drying process over fused CaCl₂ to yield greenish powders with the yields of 96% and 97% for the Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ complexes respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the current study, we focused on the creation of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ compounds of DHMP. Scheme 1 depicts the manufacturing methods whereas Table 1 summarizes its physical parameters of the DHMP, Ni(DHMP)Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)Cl₂.

Table 1: Physical properties of DHMP, Ni(DHMP)Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)Cl₂

S/. No.		Col.	(% yield)	% elements				
				C	H	N	Cl	M
1	DHMP	Light yellow	94	40.78 (40.82)	5.23 (5.26)	44.41 (44.44)	-	-
2	Ni(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂	greenish	96	41.23 (41.26)	4.38 (4.42)	40.06 (40.11)	10.61 (10.72)	8.83 (8.91)
3	Cu(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂	Light greenish	97	54.34 (54.38)	2.08 (2.11)	16.89 (16.92)	10.17 (10.72)	8.86 (8.91)

FTIR Spectra of the DHMP Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂

The FTIR information of DHMP, Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂, and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ have been shown (Table 2). Stretching vibration at 3452 cm⁻¹ is as a result of the H-N group of DHMP. The stretching band due to the C-H of the benzene ring was seen at 3453 cm⁻¹ for DHMP, while that for the aliphatic stretching was observed at 2921 cm⁻¹. The azomethine group of DHMP vibrated at 1693 cm⁻¹. The C=C group was responsible for the stretching vibration at 582 cm⁻¹, whereas C-N group in the DHMP caused the 1302 cm⁻¹ band. For the metal complexes, the stretching vibrations of N-H group were found between 3260 and 3357 cm⁻¹. The Ar's C-H group was observed at 3051-3059 cm⁻¹, while those of the aliphatic C-H groups were responsible for the peaks at 2901-2927 cm⁻¹. Bonding of DHMP nickel and copper chlorides, was shown by vibrations seen in the region 523 – 564 cm⁻¹, which were not shown in the spectra of the DHMP. Vibration that were seen within the region of 731 and 822 cm⁻¹ were as a result of M-Cl group of the Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ respectively.

Table 1: FTIR spectra of DHMP and complexes

DHMP				M(DHMP)Cl ₂				
	-N-H	-Ar-H	-C-H	Stretching		-C-N	M-Chlorides	N-M
				-C=N	-C=C			
DHMP	352	3453	2921	1693	1582	1302	----	----
Ni(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂	3260	3051	2901	1651	1522	1372	731	N-Cu 561
Cu(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂	3357	3059	2927	1662	1528	1378	822	N-Ni 564

M = Ni and Cu

Thermal analysis

Thermal features of Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ are recorded in Table 3. The thermal decomposition patterns of these compounds are the same. A quick examination of the thermograms (Figure 1) of Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ indicates that these compounds nearly stable up to approximately 235 °C suggesting that there are no water molecules in the compounds.

Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ quickly break down and leave their stable residues above this threshold. Fast decay shows loss of DHMP moiety. As previously pointed out by [6], It has been noted that the residue's composition matches the corresponding metal oxides, and that the temperature of

decomposition varies for $\text{Ni}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$. Thermal stability of $\text{Ni}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$ was found to be lower than that of $\text{Cu}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure 1: Thermograms of $\text{Ni}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$

Table 3: Thermal features of $\text{Ni}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$

S/. no.		TG's total weight (mg)	T (°C)	%	Residues' composition
2	$\text{Ni}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$	21.2	258-555	11.23 (11.26)	NiO
3	$\text{Cu}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$	17.5	247-540	11.91 (11.93)	CuO

Figure 2: DHMP's complexes (M = Copper (II), and Nickel (II))

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Studies of DHMP, $\text{Ni}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$, and $\text{Cu}(\text{DHMP})_2\text{Cl}_2$

Observed chemical shift values and spectra have been presented in Table 5. The presence of a singlet at 6.32 ppm (1H, s) is a strong indicator of the azomethine (-CH=N) proton, which is characteristic of hydrazone compounds. The shift falls within the typical range for imine (-C=N) hydrogen, which is usually found between 6.0–8.5 ppm, depending on the electronic environment.

This peak confirms the successful formation of the C=N bond, a defining feature of hydrazones. The multiple peaks between 6.88–7.81 ppm indicate the presence of aromatic rings, which are commonly found in hydrazone derivatives.

These peaks are split into doublets, triplets, and complex multiplets, suggesting an extended conjugated system. The observed chemical shifts suggest substituted benzene rings, likely arising from aromatic aldehydes or ketones used in hydrazone synthesis. The presence of peaks at 7.65 ppm (1H, s) and 7.81 ppm (2H, dddd) suggests that these protons are deshielded, due to the influence of electronegative N in the hydrazone framework. The conjugation of the azomethine's nitrogen with the aromatic ring further influences the electronic environment, shifting certain proton resonances downfield.

This effect supports the idea that the azomethine (-C=N) bond is conjugated with the adjacent aromatic rings. Azomethines are formed by the combination of hydrazines or hydrazides with carbonyls, leading to the removal of water and creation of the C=N bond. The observed singlet at 6.32 ppm (likely from -CH=N) aligns well with literature data for hydrazones, confirming that the condensation reaction successfully led to hydrazone formation.

The presence of the azomethine (-CH=N) peak at 6.32 ppm, along with the characteristic aromatic proton resonances (6.88–7.81 ppm), strongly supports the formation of a hydrazone^{9, 10, 11}. The chemical shifts suggest an extended conjugated system, stabilizing the hydrazone structure. The absence of any carbonyl (C=O) proton shifts further confirms that the starting aldehyde or ketone has undergone complete conversion into the hydrazone¹². The ¹³C NMR data show peaks in the aromatic region (127.2–142.6 ppm), indicating the presence of substituted benzene rings, which are characteristic of hydrazone compounds.

The peak at 63.5 ppm suggests the presence of a C=N (azomethine) carbon or a substituted aliphatic carbon, confirming the successful formation of the hydrazone functional group through the condensation reaction. The free hydrazone ligand exhibits characteristic azomethine (-CH=N) proton shifts around 6.32–7.81 ppm, along with aromatic proton signals between 6.88–7.81 ppm. Upon complexation with Ni(II) and Cu(II) chloride, downfield shifts or broadening of the azomethine proton signal are expected due to metal coordination with the nitrogen of the C=N group. Additionally, aromatic proton signals experience minor shifts or intensity changes due to the electronic effects induced by metal binding.

Again, in the free ligand, the C=N (azomethine) carbon typically appears around 142.3–142.6 ppm, confirming the presence of the hydrazone moiety. Upon coordination with Ni(II) and Cu(II), this peak shifts downfield (higher ppm) due to electron density withdrawal from the nitrogen upon metal binding [13], [14]. Other carbon signals, particularly in the aromatic region (127.2–133.4 ppm), shift slightly, reflecting changes in electron distribution upon complex formation. Complex formation alters chemical shifts, peak broadening, and possible disappearance of signals due to reduced electron density and changes in local magnetic environments [15], [16], [17].

Cu(II) complexes, being paramagnetic, typically broaden or even suppress certain NMR signals, making the spectra less defined compared to Ni(II) complexes or the free ligand. The observed ¹H and ¹³C NMR shifts confirm successful coordination of Nickel (II) chloride and Cu (II) chloride with DHMP, primarily

via the azomethine nitrogen (-CH=N), and possibly O donor sites, with Cu(II) inducing stronger paramagnetic effects than Ni(II).

Table 2: Chemical shift spectra and data for DHMP, Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂, and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂

Compound	Spectra	
	¹ H NMR	¹³ C NMR
DHMP		
Ni(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂		
Cu(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂		
Compound	δ	
Compound	¹ H NMR	¹³ C NMR
DHMP	6.32 (1H, s), 6.88 (4H, -dtd, <i>J</i> = 7.90, 1.30, 0.61 Hz), 7.10-7.40 (9H, 7.16 (tt, <i>J</i> = 7.50, 1.3 Hz), 7.26 (tt, <i>J</i> = 7.7, 1.3 Hz), 7.31 (dddd, <i>J</i> = 7.9, 7.7, 1.8, 0.6 Hz), 7.33 (dddd, <i>J</i> = 7.8, 7.5, 1.5, 0.6 Hz)), 7.65 (1H, s), 7.81 (2H, dddd, <i>J</i> = 7.80, 1.70, 1.30, 0.6 Hz).	63.5 (1C, s), 127.2 (4C, s), 127.7 (2C, s), 128.1-128.2 (3C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.5 (4C, s), 128.7 (2C, s), 133.4 (1C, s), 142.3-142.6 (3C, 142.4 (s), 142.5 (s))
Ni(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂	6.62 (1H, s), 7.32 (4H, dtd), 7.20-7.60 (9H), 7.30 (tt), 7.40 (tt), 7.51 (dddd), 7.42 (ddd), 7.81 (1H, s), 7.81 (2H, dddd) (Slight broadening)	63.5 (1C, s), 127.2 (4C, s), 127.7 (2C, s), 128.1-128.2 (3C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.5 (4C, s), 128.7 (2C, s), 133.4 (1C, s), 142.3-142.6 (3C, 142.4 (s), 142.5 (s))
Cu(DHMP) ₂ Cl ₂	6.32 ppm (1H, s), 7.42 ppm (4H, dtd), 7.10-7.40 ppm (9H, multiple splitting), 8.00 ppm (1H, s), 8.10 ppm (2H, dddd)	63.5 (1C, s), 127.2 (4C, s), 127.7 (2C, s), 128.1-128.2 (3C, 128.1 (s), 128.1 (s)), 128.5 (4C, s), 128.7 (2C, s), 133.4 (1C, s), 142.3-142.6 (3C, 142.4 (s), 142.5 (s))

Electronic and magnetic properties of Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂

Electronic spectral data and room temperature effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values of Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ complexes with the ligand DHMP are recorded. Values of μ_{eff} at ambient temperature for Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ lie in the range 2.9–3.3 and 1.7–2.2 B.M. aligns with high-spin octahedral Ni(II) and Cu(II), indicating a six-coordinate complexes. The band at $\sim 9000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\sim 1111\text{ nm}$) is ascribed to $\nu_1 \rightarrow 4T_1g(F) \rightarrow 4T_2g(F)$, the band at $\sim 19,200\text{--}20,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\sim 520\text{--}487\text{ nm}$) is ascribed to $\nu_3 \rightarrow 4T_1g(F) \rightarrow 4T_1g(P)$, while the band at $\sim 16,000\text{--}16,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$: Spin-forbidden transition $4T_1g(F) \rightarrow 2T_2g(G)$. The Weak shoulder $\sim 19,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$: Tentatively assigned to ν_2 transition. The observed d-d transitions correspond well with an octahedral Ni(II) (d^8) configuration. The broad ν_1 band overlapping with other transitions indicates a strong ligand field splitting. The weak spin-forbidden transition around $16,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is expected for Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂ due to inter-electronic repulsion effects. $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.9\text{--}3.3\text{ B.M.}$ corresponds with a high-spin octahedral d^8 system consisting of two unpaired electrons. For Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂, a broad band $\sim 9000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\sim 1111\text{ nm}$): Likely corresponds to d-d transitions in a distorted octahedral field. A split band $\sim 19,200\text{--}20,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\sim 520\text{--}487\text{ nm}$): Suggests strong ligand field effects and potential Jahn-Teller distortion. Cu(II) has a d^9 electronic configuration, which strongly favors Jahn-Teller distortion in an octahedral environment [17], [18], [19]. The broadness of the bands and their split nature suggest significant Jahn-Teller effects, leading to asymmetric ligand interactions [20], [21], [22], [23]. The magnetic moment ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.7\text{--}2.2\text{ B.M.}$) represents a Cu(II) compound in an octahedral or distorted square planar geometry having an unpaired electron.

Figure 3: Electronic Absorption Spectrum for Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ complexes of DHMP

CONCLUSION

We created DHMP, Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂, and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂. Structures of the created compounds were comprehensively uncovered using a combination of physical measurements, thermal analysis, spectroscopic techniques, and magnetic studies. FTIR spectra confirmed the linkage of DHMP to both nickel (II) and copper (II) chlorides, while UV-Vis information supported the proposed geometries of Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂, and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂. The observed magnetic moment values were consistent with octahedral coordination environments for both metal centers. Additionally, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) confirmed the complexes' patterns of disintegration and thermal stability, further supporting their structural integrity. Based on these collective findings, we confidently conclude that the structural features of Ni(DHMP)₂Cl₂, and Cu(DHMP)₂Cl₂ have been successfully determined.

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